
Increasing English Translation Skill through Grammar Translation Method at the Fifth Semester Students of English Education Program at STKIP Kie Raha Ternate

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Abstract

This study aims to describe the improvement of translation skills through a combination of the grammar-translation method. This study shows that the students' translation skills have not improved significantly. This can be seen from the achievement of student understanding. The results obtained through a questionnaire show that the translation course is very liked by 66.7 percent of students. Meanwhile, other aspects have not been seen to increase optimally. For assignments/exercises the percentage of 53.3 percent of students showed sufficient results. Meanwhile, for the implications and benefits aspects, the achievement was only in the range of 13.3 percent and the benefits aspect of 20.0 percent.

Keywords: *Skill, grammar-translation method, GTM, skill improving, teaching method*

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1. Background

In the 2019 KKNI-based Curriculum for the English Education Study Program of STKIP Kie Raha Ternate, translation courses are included in the courses established in the field of communication and translation skills studies. This course aims to train students to translate simple and short texts from English into Indonesian, and vice versa.

The translation is one of the skills in language teaching. The translation is a simple process, which is a process that aims to interpret word for word from the source language to the target language. According to Newmark (1988, p. 7):

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“As a technique for learning foreign languages, translation is a two-edged instrument: it has the special purpose of demonstrating the learner's knowledge of the foreign language, either as a form of control or to exercise his intelligence to develop his competence.”

Newmark's statement above can be interpreted that as a technique in teaching foreign languages, translation has two important objectives, including translation to show students' knowledge of mastery of foreign languages, both (1) translation aims as a form of control of foreign language mastery, or (2) translation as an exercise in intelligence in developing language competencies that students have in tertiary institutions.

The problem that was found in the fifth-semester students of the English Education Study Program of STKIP Kie Raha Ternate was that the level of understanding and translation skills was not yet optimal. This is influenced by grammar mastery, reading content, translation meanings, and vocabulary.

Based on the background and problems above, the researchers tried to combine translation learning with other methods to solve these problems, namely by providing a comprehensive solution to improve the translation skills of students in the fifth semester of the 2020/2021 academic year, namely the grammar-translation method. This method is called the classical method. According to Brown (2001), this method focuses on grammatical rules, memorizing vocabulary, interpreting conjugations, translating texts, and practicing writing.

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. *Translation as a language or linguistic skill*

Linguistic competence is an absolute requirement for a prospective translator because translation is closely related to the language, source language, and target language. Wuryantoro (2019), citing the linguistic definition of Merriam-Webster, states that linguistics is "The study of human speech including the units, nature, structure, and modification of language or of or relating to language".

Catford (1965), as quoted by Halliday's (in Kuhlman and Littau, 2007) asserts that "the linguistic framework and applied it to translation, including the notion of a shift to account for the departure from formal correspondence that takes place when the original text is translated into the target language".

According to Munday (2016), the term translation has several meanings:

"It can refer to the general subject field, the product (the text that has been translated), or the process (the act of producing the translation, otherwise known as translating). The process of translation between two different languages written involves the translator changing an original written text (the source text or ST) in the original verbal language (the source language or SL) into a written text (the target text or TT) in a different verbal language (the target language or TL)".

2.2. *The grammar-translation method*

According to Rafli and Lustyantje (2016), this method is based on the assumption that there is one "universal logic" which is the basis of all languages in this world, and grammar is a branch of logic.

Brown (2001) shows that in the 21st century, a classic method known as the grammar-translation method emerged. Furthermore, according to him, there are several differences from the grammar-translation used in foreign language learning in the classroom which focuses on grammatical rules as the basis for translation from the second language to the mother tongue. This is by the opinion of Prator and Celce-Murcia (1979) quoted by Brown (2001), that there are several characteristics of this method, namely:

1. Classes are taught in the mother tongue, with little active use of the target language.
2. Much vocabulary is taught in the form of a list of isolated work
3. A long, elaborate explanation of the intricacies of grammar are given
4. Grammar provides the rules for putting words together, and instruction often focuses on the form and inflection of words.
5. Reading of difficult classical texts is begun early
6. Little attention is paid to the content of the text, which is treated as exercises in grammatical analysis
7. Often the only drills are exercises in translating disconnected sentences from the target language into the mother tongue.
8. Little or no attention is given to pronunciation

Munday (2016) states that in the linguistic area, translation has several aspects: (1) the general subject field or phenomenon ('I studied translation at university'), (2) the product - that is, the text that has been translated ('they published the Arabic translation of the report'), and (3) the process of producing the translation, otherwise known as translating ('translation service').

3. Method

3.1. *Research Design*

In this study, researchers used a qualitative research design. According to Creswell (2013), this qualitative research process involves important efforts, such as asking questions and procedures, collecting specific data from participants, analyzing data inductively ranging from specific themes to general themes, and interpreting the meaning of the data.

3.2. *Participants*

The population in this research was all students of the English Department of STKIP Kie Raha Ternate, and the samples of this research were 20 fifth-semester students of the English department of STKIP Kie Raha Ternate.

3.3. *Techniques of Data Collection and Data Analysis*

In this study, researchers used a questionnaire as a data collection instrument. This questionnaire serves to assess students' ability to answer questions. The data analysis used by researchers used descriptive analysis using the SPSS program to see the improvement in

student translation skills after using the grammar-translation method. Iskandar (2008) states that the SPSS program can be used in analyzing descriptive data, namely determining the frequency, percent, mean, median, standard deviation, and variance.

4. Finding and Discussion

4.1. Results from the questionnaire

The results of the questionnaire analysis using the SPSS application showed the following results:

Do you like the translation subject?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	10	66.7	66.7	66.7
Sometimes	5	33.3	33.3	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Do you like to learn translation with the grammar-translation method?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	7	46.7	46.7	46.7
Sometimes	7	46.7	46.7	93.3
No	1	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Do you think that translation skill is required as a language skill?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	4	26.7	26.7	26.7
Sometimes	6	40.0	40.0	66.7
No	5	33.3	33.3	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Do you comprehend the material delivered by your teacher in translation subject?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	10	66.7	66.7	66.7
Sometimes	5	33.3	33.3	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Do you find any difficulties in learning translation?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	9	60.0	60.0	60.0
Sometimes	6	40.0	40.0	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

After going with the grammar-translation method, do you experience any improvement in translation?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	5	33.3	33.3	33.3
Sometimes	8	53.3	53.3	86.7
No	2	13.3	13.3	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Do you find any difficulties in translating text from a source language to a target language?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	8	53.3	53.3	53.3
Sometimes	5	33.3	33.3	86.7
No	2	13.3	13.3	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Do you understand the overall material in the translation subject with the grammar-translation method?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	10	66.7	66.7	66.7
Sometimes	4	26.7	26.7	93.3
No	1	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Do you find it easier to translate with the grammar-translation method?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	7	46.7	46.7	46.7
Sometimes	7	46.7	46.7	93.3
No	1	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Do you find that the grammar-translation method fun?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	7	46.7	46.7	46.7
Sometimes	7	46.7	46.7	93.3
No	1	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Does your teacher give you translation exercises during the course?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	6	40.0	40.0	40.0
Sometimes	6	40.0	40.0	80.0
No	3	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

During the course, are you usually given homework in translation?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	2	13.3	13.3	13.3
Sometimes	6	40.0	40.0	53.3
No	7	46.7	46.7	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Does your teacher use a lesson plan?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	5	33.3	33.3	33.3
Sometimes	7	46.7	46.7	80.0
No	3	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Do the exercises and homework help you to learn how to translate effectively?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	8	53.3	53.3	53.3
Sometimes	3	20.0	20.0	73.3
No	4	26.7	26.7	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Do you find that the grammar-translation method helpful?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	3	20.0	20.0	20.0
Sometimes	9	60.0	60.0	80.0
No	3	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Based on the results of data analysis carried out from 15 item questions from the research variables, the researcher found that the translation course was very popular with 66.7 percent of students. Meanwhile, 46.7 percent of students indicated that they understood the grammar-translation method. While the understanding of translation in the aspect of language skills, only 26.7 students showed good results. The understanding of the translation course material taught was only responded well by 66.7 students. 53.3 percent of students have difficulty translating text from the source language to the target language. Only 46.7 percent of students considered learning with the grammar-translation method fun. And finally, teaching translation using the grammar-translation method only shows 13.3 percent implications and 20 percent benefits.

5. Conclusion

Based on the data analysis above, the researcher concludes that translation learning through the grammar-translation method has not shown a significant improvement in translation skills. Although most students responded that they enjoyed the learning enough, their understanding did not experience the expected improvement.

Researchers suggest that in teaching translation carried out by lecturers, it is better to provide additional assignments and training. Students are given the task of translating articles in English into Indonesian and examples of good and correct translation guided by the lecturer. Translation learning innovations are highly recommended for teachers of translation courses.

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